

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review Article On Osteoporosis A Global Perspective On Bone Health

Komal Chavan, Kavita Kulkarni, Sanchit Deshpande*

Gajanan Maharaj College Of Pharmacy ,Chh.Sambhajinagar

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 20 Oct 2024

Keywords:

osteoporosis, fracture, bone mineral, bone density, menopause, calcium.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13957903

ABSTRACT

Osteoporosis is a widespread condition that causes a significant loss of bone density and strength, making bones more susceptible to fractures. It is especially common in older adults and can lead to serious health issues and even death. Many people don't realize they have osteoporosis until they suffer a fracture, as it often develops quietly over time. Globally, over 200 million people are affected by osteoporosis, resulting in around 2 million hip fractures each year, as well as other severe bone injuries. The disease is influenced by several factors, including genetics, hormonal changes, physical activity, and nutrition. In 1994, the World Health Organization (WHO) set standards for diagnosing osteoporosis, which helped improve the technology used to measure bone mineral density (BMD) in various body parts.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoporosis is a condition where bones, although fully mineralized, become porous and weak, making them more susceptible to fractures. This significant loss of bone mass mainly affects older adults, who are especially vulnerable to the disease. "Established osteoporosis" refers to individuals who have already suffered at least one fragility fracture from minimal trauma. Over 200 million people worldwide have osteoporosis, leading to around 2 million hip fractures each year, with this number projected to increase significantly in the next 50 years. In addition to hip fractures, osteoporosis can cause other serious fractures, such as compression fractures of the

vertebrae, which can severely impact a person's quality of life. The World Health Organization defines osteoporosis as having a bone mineral density (BMD) that is 2.5 standard deviations or more below the average for healthy adults, measured using a dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) scan.

Causes of osteoporosis:

Common Causes:

1. Old Age:

As people age, their bones naturally become weaker. The cells that build new bone (osteoblasts) become less effective, leading to more bone loss than replacement.

***Corresponding Author:** Sanchit Deshpande

Address: Gajanan Maharaj College Of Pharmacy ,Chh.Sambhajinagar

Email ✉: Sanchitdeshpande07@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

2. Immobility:

Being inactive or bedridden means bones don't get the stress and movement they need to stay strong. This lack of mechanical force can lead to rapid bone density loss, particularly in the spine.

3. Menopause:

After menopause, women produce less estrogen, a hormone that helps protect bones. This drop can result in quicker bone loss, though the rate varies from woman to woman.

Less Common Causes:

1. Cushing's Syndrome:

This condition involves high cortisol levels, which can weaken bones. People taking corticosteroid medications often experience similar bone loss.

2. Hypogonadism:

Low levels of sex hormones, such as testosterone in men, can lead to weaker bones, often going unrecognized as a cause of osteoporosis.

3. Hypopituitarism:

When the pituitary gland doesn't produce enough hormones, it can negatively affect bone health.

How These Conditions Affect Bone Health:

- **Old Age:**

Less effective osteoblasts result in more bone loss.

- **Immobility:**

Lack of movement leads to significant bone loss due to insufficient stimulation.

- **Menopause:**

Decreased estrogen is linked to bone loss, with rates varying among individuals.

- **Cushing's Syndrome:**

High cortisol levels reduce the activity of osteoblasts, weakening bones.

Risk factors for osteoporosis:

1. Age

- **Older Age:**

As people get older, their bones naturally lose density. This is especially true for women after menopause.

2. Gender

- **Women:**

Women are at a higher risk, particularly after menopause, due to the drop in estrogen levels, which is important for maintaining bone density.

3. Family History

- **Genetics:**

If osteoporosis runs in your family, you might have a higher chance of developing it yourself. A family history of fractures can also be a warning sign.

4. Hormonal Changes

- **Menopause:**

The decline in estrogen levels during menopause significantly increases the risk of osteoporosis in women.

- **Low Testosterone:**

In men, low testosterone levels can also contribute to bone loss.

5. Dietary Factors

- **Low Calcium Intake:**

Not getting enough calcium in your diet can weaken bones.

- **Vitamin D Deficiency:**

Vitamin D is essential for calcium absorption. A lack of it can lead to bone loss.

6. Lifestyle Choices

- **Sedentary Lifestyle:**

Not getting enough physical activity, especially weight-bearing exercises, can contribute to weaker bones.

- **Smoking:**

Smoking is harmful to bone health and increases the risk of osteoporosis.

- **Excessive Alcohol:**

Drinking too much alcohol can interfere with the body's ability to absorb calcium and may contribute to bone loss.

Management of disease:

1. Diet:

a. Calcium:

Aim for 1,000-1,200 mg of calcium daily. Foods like dairy products, leafy greens, almonds, and fortified foods can help.

b. Vitamin D:

This helps your body absorb calcium. You can get it from sunlight, fatty fish, egg yolks, and fortified foods. Supplements might be needed, especially in winter or for those with limited sun exposure.

2. Exercise:

a. Weight-Bearing Activities:

Engage in activities that make you work against gravity, like walking, jogging, dancing, and weight training. These help strengthen bones.

b. Balance and Flexibility:

Yoga or tai chi can improve balance, reducing the risk of falls and fractures.

3. Medication:

Depending on your risk level, your doctor may prescribe medications like bisphosphonates (e.g., Alendronate) to help strengthen bones or other treatments like hormone therapy. It's essential to discuss the best options for you with your healthcare provider.

4. Lifestyle Changes:

a. Quit Smoking:

Smoking can weaken bones, so quitting is crucial.

b. Limit Alcohol:

Heavy drinking can increase your risk of fractures. Stick to moderate consumption.

c. Maintain a Healthy Weight:

Being underweight can increase bone loss.

5. Fall Prevention:

Home Safety: Remove tripping hazards, use non-slip mats, and ensure good lighting in your home.

Vision and Hearing Checks: Regular check-ups can help prevent falls.

6. Regular Check-Ups:

Get bone density tests as recommended by your doctor to monitor your bone health.

7. Educate Yourself:

Understanding osteoporosis and how to manage it is empowering. Stay informed about the latest treatments and research.

8. Regular Monitoring:

Bone Density Tests:

Regular check-ups with bone density tests (DXA scans) can help monitor your bone health. These tests measure how dense and strong your bones.

CONCLUSION:

osteoporosis is a major public health issue that impacts millions globally, especially older adults and postmenopausal women. It leads to weakened bones and a higher risk of fractures, which can cause serious health problems and lower quality of life. There are effective treatment options available, from lifestyle changes to medications. However, many high-risk individuals, particularly those who have already had fractures, go undiagnosed and untreated. This highlights the need for increased awareness, early detection, and proactive measures to tackle osteoporosis.

REFERENCES:

1. National Institute of Health. Osteoporosis prevention, diagnosis, and therapy. Consensus Statement. Bethesda, MD: National Institutes of Health; 2000; 17:1-36
2. Goodman TA, Simon LS. Osteoporosis: Current issue in diagnosis and management. *J Musculoskel Med.* 1997; 14: 10-22.
3. Kanis JA. Diagnosis of osteoporosis and assessment of fracture risk. *Lancet* 2002; 359: 1929-1936.
4. Consensus development conference 199 I Prophylaxis and treatment of osteoporosis. *Am J Med* 90:107-110.
5. World Health Organisation 1994 Assessment of fracture risk and its application to screening for postmenopausal osteoporosis. Technical Report Series. WHO, Geneva.
6. Riggs BL, Melton U HI: Medical progress series: Involutional osteoporosis. *N Engl J Med* 1986; 314:1676
7. Peck WA, Riggs BL, Bell NH, et al: Research directions in osteoporosis. Scientific Workshop. *Am J Med* 1988; 84:275
8. Dequeker J, Nijs J, Verstraeten A, Geusens P, Gevers G: Genetic determinants of bone mineral content at the spine and radius: A twin study. *Bone* 1987; 8:207
9. Heaney RP, Gallagher JC, Johnston CC, Neer R, Parfitt AM, Whedon GD: Calcium nutrition and bone health in the elderly. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1982; 36:986
10. Tsai K-S, Heath H III, Kumar R, Riggs BL: Impaired vitamin D metabolism with aging in women: Possible role in pathogenesis of senile osteoporosis. *J Clin Invest* 1984; 73:1668
11. Mary L. Bouxsein, , John Kaufman, , Laura Tosi, ,Steven Cummings, Joseph Lane, and Olof Johnell. Recommendations for Optimal Care of the Fragility Fracture Patient to Reduce the Risk of Future Fracture. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg.* 2004; 12(6): 385-395.

HOW TO CITE: Komal Chavan, Kavita Kulkarni, Sanchit Deshpande, A Review Article On Osteoporosis A Global Perspective On Bone Health, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 10, 1170-1173. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13957903>